

Research

Comparative Study of Privacy Models: Evaluating the Effectiveness Against Different Attacker Models

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Abstract: In the current digital era, organizations often collect personal data from individuals and store it in databases that contain personally identifiable information (PII). Sharing this data with researchers can pose significant privacy risks. To mitigate these risks, several data privacy models have been proposed. In this study, the effectiveness of four privacy models (k-anonymity, l-diversity, t-closeness, and differential privacy) is evaluated by comparing the output results of three different attacker models: journalist, prosecutor, and marketer. Utilizing an adult dataset, each privacy model is applied, and the output results of the attacker models are compared to identify the most effective privacy protection model. The results indicate that, while not offering the highest data utility compared to other privacy models, differential privacy provides the most robust protection against all three attacker models. The choice of privacy model ultimately depends on the specific scenario and the balance between privacy protection and data utility that is required. The study contributes valuable insights for professionals and researchers within the data privacy domain.

Keywords: Data Privacy Models, Differential Privacy, Attacker Models, Privacy Protection, Data Utility, Privacy Study

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Accepted: 31 January, 2024; **Published:** 22 February, 2024

How to cite this article: Muhammad Usman Naveed, Lu Zhimao, Muhammad Usama Amin, Abdur Rehman, Muhammad Adil (2024). *Comparative Study of Privacy Models: Evaluating the Effectiveness Against Different Attacker Models*. *North American Academic Research*, 7(1), 82-93. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10711116>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Certainly! The need for data anonymization techniques has become more pressing in recent years due to the increased collection and analysis of data in a variety of industries, including healthcare, finance, and marketing. As data becomes more valuable, it also becomes more vulnerable to misuse, theft, and unauthorized access. Therefore, it is important to protect the privacy of individuals while still allowing the analysis of data to derive meaningful insights and hence maintaining the utility [1]. Maintaining a balance between data value and data privacy is a significant task [2].

Traditional anonymization techniques such as k-anonymity^[3], l-diversity^[4], and t-closeness^[5] have been widely used to protect the privacy of individuals. These techniques have been effective in certain contexts, such as when data is relatively homogenous and there are no external data sources available to attackers. However, recent studies have shown that these techniques can be vulnerable to attacks that leverage external data sources to re-identify individuals in a dataset.

To address these limitations, new anonymization techniques such as differential privacy^[6] randomized response, and secure multi-party computation have emerged. These techniques provide stronger privacy guarantees by adding noise to the data or by distributing the computation across multiple parties. Differential privacy, for example, ensures that the output of a computation does not reveal anything about the input data except for the intended result. Randomized response, on the other hand, provides plausible deniability by adding noise to individual responses, making it difficult to determine whether a particular individual gave a specific response. Secure multi-party computation allows multiple parties to jointly compute a function without revealing their inputs, providing a way to perform computations on sensitive data without compromising privacy.

In the field of healthcare, the infringement of patients' privacy has become an escalating issue, particularly in the area of big data analysis. To safeguard patients' identities, data anonymization is utilized before conducting any analytics^[7]. Although privacy concerns persist, data sharing and publishing are still prevalent. However, multiple pieces of data that have been shared or published with external parties can be amalgamated to create a comprehensive data set. As an illustration, medical data can be obtained by combining patient information with public voter registration lists, or by obtaining data from publicly distributed questionnaires and amalgamating it with published data. As per findings from specific researchers, the accurate identification of nearly 60% of individuals becomes possible by employing an individual's date of birth, zip code, and gender.^[8] By means of a linkage attack, it is possible to identify most individuals by utilizing these particular attributes and inferring sensitive attribute values of the targeted victim^[9].

Recent research has shown that differential privacy and secure multi-party computation can provide stronger privacy guarantees than traditional techniques in many contexts. However, these techniques may come at the cost of increased computational complexity and reduced utility. Therefore, the choice of anonymization technique depends on the specific context and the trade-offs between privacy, utility, and computational complexity.

This paper assesses the effectiveness of various anonymization techniques, including k-anonymity, l-diversity, t-closeness, and differential privacy, using four metrics: prosecutor attack risk, journalist attack risk, marketer attack risk, and data utility. Prosecutor attack risk measures the risk of re-identification when attacker have the background knowledge, journalist attack risk measures the re-identification risk when an attacker targets a particular person, mostly targets the celebrities. Marketer Attack risk measures when the attacker wants to re identify large amount of data. The data utility is measured using the granularity metric, which gauges the level of detail and specificity in the anonymized data.

Background

The concept of privacy has been historically associated with the entitlements of an individual. Article 12 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which was adopted in 1948, explicitly affirms this principle which states that "No one shall be subjected to arbitrary interference with his privacy, family, home or correspondence, nor to attacks upon his honor and reputation. Everyone has the right to the protection of the law against such interference or attacks"^[10]. Hence, this Act allows us to ascertain the significance of an individual's privacy.

The goal of this section is to describe the main concepts and work in the field of data privacy research.

Evaluation of various data anonymization methods is conducted to enable the sharing of data with external entities or organizations. This involves implementing appropriate technical measures to mitigate potential risks related to the unauthorized exposure of sensitive information. The removal of identifiers from raw data is definitely important to ensure individual privacy, but it is not adequate to ensure the individual privacy. As an example, sweeny^[3] showed in

his article that around 87% of the person specific data (216 million of 248 million) of the population in the United States can be re identified by just three quasi-identifiers: Gender, Birth Date and Zip Code. Later the new researcher ^[11] corrected the estimation of re identification 61-63%. Which is still too high.

To address these issues many researchers did a lot of work in this field. Most of the famous data privacy models to protect person specific information are: k-anonymity, l-diversity, t-closeness and differential privacy.

K-anonymity:

One of the most popular and extensively utilized privacy models is k-anonymity, which seeks to render each entry indistinguishable from at least k-1 other entries. Achieving k-anonymity generally involves a computational process that combines global or local attribute recoding with local suppressions ^[3, 12].

For attributes with no clear hierarchy, micro aggregation is a suitable alternative procedure ^[13]. In order to implement k-anonymity, identifiers are removed from the data and quasi-identifier attributes, such as age, gender, zip code, and race, are masked to prevent re-identification. Confidential attributes, such as salary or health condition, are not masked unless they are also quasi-identifiers. While k-anonymity has been demonstrated to be an effective method for anonymization, particularly for small values of k, it is still susceptible to attacks that exploit a lack of diversity in non-anonymized confidential attributes or additional background knowledge available to the attacker ^[4, 5, 14, 15].

L-diversity:

A limitation of simple k-Anonymity is that even if there are k individuals for each quasi-identifier, it does not ensure diversity in the confidential attribute values associated with those groups. For example, all individuals in a group may have the same medical diagnosis, come from the same region, or belong to the same religion. In such cases, having k individuals is not sufficient to ensure confidentiality, as the confidential attribute is the same for all individuals. If an individual is known to exist in the dataset, the confidentiality of their sensitive information can be compromised ^[16]. The l-Diversity model is designed to address the limitation of k-Anonymity by requiring a minimum number of distinct confidential attribute values within each group of k individuals. This approach aims to prevent attribute disclosure and improve the protection of sensitive information in the data set.

T-closeness

Despite l-diversity effectiveness in preventing certain types of attacks, the l-diversity model has its own set of weaknesses. Specifically, it is vulnerable to specialized attacks like skewness and similarity attacks, which exploit the fact that l-diversity does not take into account the overall distribution of attributes in the entire database.

T-closeness is an extension of the k-anonymity mechanism ^[5]. In contrast to k-anonymity, t-closeness involves modifying the values of sensitive attributes in each equivalence class. T-closeness ensures that the empirical distributions of a sensitive attribute within an equivalence class and in the entire table do not differ by a value greater than a predefined threshold t. As a result, t-closeness is considered a more robust notion of privacy than k-anonymity.

Differential Privacy

In contrast to other privacy models, ϵ -differential privacy is a more recent and stricter approach that does not make any assumptions about the attacker's knowledge. This method guarantees that the anonymized output is insensitive (up to a factor that depends on ϵ) to changes in individual input records, thereby ensuring that an individual's privacy is not compromised by their inclusion in the dataset. This guarantee is more robust than that offered by the k-anonymity model. To achieve this, ϵ -differential privacy adds a certain amount of noise to the data to obtain the anonymized output, which depends on the variability of the original non-anonymized values. Originally designed for interactive scenarios, ϵ -differential privacy allows the anonymizer to return answers to interactive queries with added noise instead of releasing an anonymized version of the entire dataset ^[6].

In order to effectively anonymize a dataset, it is crucial to understand the characteristics of the information being recorded. These characteristics refer to how the data operates beyond its explicit content, with a specific focus on privacy and its associated hazards. Various pieces of information, such as names, ages, medical diagnoses, or even preferred ice

cream flavors, possess their own semantic significance and serve different purposes when analyzed as part of a dataset. However, during the anonymization procedure, they exhibit distinct properties that dictate how they must be handled. A person's name is potentially personally identifiable; while an age may not explicitly reveal a person's identity, it could in conjunction with other details; a medical diagnosis typically does not disclose an individual's identity but requires confidentiality and is often the target of anonymization; in contrast, a favorite ice cream flavor is generally not considered sensitive information and offers minimal value for identifying a person.

These illustrations showcase the four types of attributes that a microdata set could encompass:

Identifiers refer to data that can be exploited by a malicious party to directly determine an individual's identity, including a name, social security number, or address [16].

Quasi-identifiers, closely related to identifiers, may lead to re-identification of an individual within a dataset but require additional quasi-identifiers to accomplish this, such as age, nationality, and gender [16]. The notion of an equivalence class, defined by Domingo-Ferrer et al. when introducing the k-anonymity privacy model, consists of a combination of quasi-identifier values.

Confidential attributes, on the other hand, consist of sensitive data that must be safeguarded and could result in negative repercussions if disclosed [16]. What constitutes sensitive information is often subjective, but certain regulations may specify particular types of data that require protection, such as health-related data, religious beliefs, and sexual orientation [16].

Finally, non-confidential attributes: are pieces of information that neither allow for direct or indirect identification of an individual nor require protection. Such information may appear insignificant to most individuals but could be significant for particular purposes, such as market research conducted by an ice cream manufacturer based on people's favorite flavors.

Related Work

Data publishers face the challenge of selecting a suitable privacy model to protect privacy while sharing data. Therefore, evaluating the trade-off between the data utility and privacy offered by different privacy models is a significant area of research. Several privacy models, such as k-anonymity [3], t-closeness [5], l-diversity [4], and Differential privacy [17], are prominent in this area. A comprehensive discussion on these models and their extensions is provided in [18]. Priyank Jain et al [19] compared different approaches for preserving privacy in the context of big data. Most of the authors compare the privacy models on the basis of the information loss or granularity of the anonymized data [1]. Atul Kumar did the comparative analysis of the different anonymization techniques like generalization and slicing [20]. The authors Domingo-Ferrer and J. Soria-Comas conducted a comparison between the privacy protections offered by implementing k-anonymity and ϵ -differential privacy [21].

In [22], the authors analyze and compare various clustering-based algorithms for k-anonymization. They argue that the usefulness of an anonymization approach should be evaluated based on the level of utility it offers for the intended applications. In addition, the author in [23] introduce a framework for evaluating and comparing various Privacy-Preserving Data Mining (PPDM) algorithms. In the field of SDC, there have been comparative studies and frameworks introduced to evaluate the efficiency of microdata anonymization methods in terms of the risk of disclosure and information loss, as discussed in [24].

Methodology

My study aims to answer the question "How do k-anonymity, l-diversity, t-closeness, and differential privacy models compare in terms of their ability to protect against different attacker models while preserving data utility?"

In this study I utilize the adult dataset from the UC Irvine machine learning repository. This dataset contains information collected from the US census. Then I preprocess the dataset by cleaning and transforming the dataset to be ready for anonymization. I used the ARX tool which have the graphical interface. For the privacy models, I used k-anonymity, l-diversity, t-closeness, and ϵ -differential privacy which are the well-known privacy models used for

anonymizing the dataset. All simulations were conducted using the widely utilized ARX tool, specifically designed for anonymizing data. ARX tool also provides support for various data privacy and quality models that can serve as objective functions for optimizing the output of an anonymization process.

After applying the privacy models, I evaluate the effectiveness of the applied privacy models I compared the output results of three attacker models, i.e., journalist attacker model, prosecutor attacker model, and marketer model. Journalist attacker model, measures the re-identification risk when an attacker targets a particular person, mostly targets the celebrities. Prosecutor attacker model, measures the risk of re-identification when attacker have the background knowledge. Marketer Attack model, measures when the attacker wants to reidentify large amount of data.

I compute the risk scores for each attacker model based on the disclosed information. To measure the data quality of the anonymized dataset I used the granularity and generalization metrics, which are the essential metrics to measure the utility of the data. Then I compare the results of the applied privacy models based on their effectiveness in preserving privacy and the level of data utility achieved.

Experiments and Results

The main goal of experiments is to evaluate the effectiveness of the applied privacy models by comparing the output results of three attacker models, journalist attacker model, prosecutor attacker model, and marketer model. Nine attributes from the adult dataset, collected from the US Census, were utilized in the study. In pre-processing of the dataset, records with missing values are excluded. As a result, the total number of valid records is 30,162. The experiments are run on a 2.4GHZ intel core i5 machine with 8GB memory. The experiment maintained constant ARX parameters, including a suppression limit of 100% and individual attribute weights set to 0.5. By setting the suppression limit to 100%, the maximum amount of unnecessary records from the input dataset may be removed, accounting for a more realistic and practical data publication scenario [25].

In the experiments section, computations are conducted for the values of various privacy models. The risk factor of three attacker models is compared by applying different values to the privacy models. Attacker may originate from any domain aiming to compromise specific identities for journalistic purposes or targeting individuals to understand their interests for marketing purposes. Similarly, the attacker may possess background knowledge about the individual. A series of experiments was conducted with diverse parameter values for each privacy model.

Experiment 1: In this experiment, the K-anonymity privacy model is employed to address concerns related to identity disclosure. The Figure 1 illustrates the values of k for the K-anonymity model. In Figure 1, a comparison is presented for the risk factors associated with the three mentioned attacker models. To assess the effectiveness of the applied privacy model, granularity of the output data is computed. The k-anonymity parameter, k, was varied with values ranging from 2 to 25. As depicted in Figure 1, increasing the value of k correlates with a decrease in the risk of re-identifying a person's information. However, this comes at the cost of losing granularity in the data. The K-anonymity model aims to safeguard the identities of individuals in a dataset by ensuring that each individual cannot be re-identified from fewer than k-1 other individuals.

Figure 1: K-Anonymity Model Evaluation: Privacy Analysis and Attacker Model Comparison

Experiment 2: In this experiment, the l-diversity privacy model is implemented, emphasizing concerns related to attribute disclosure. Various values of l, ranging from 2 to 10, are calculated in conjunction with k-anonymity within the given dataset. For the k values (2, 5, 10, and 20), Figure 2 illustrates that increasing the value of l reduces the disclosure risk against the prosecutor, journalist, and marketer attacker models. Moreover, certain values of K yield better granularity compared to others. Specifically, at K=5, better privacy is achieved than at K=2, making it a preferable choice if 50% granularity is acceptable. Similarly, if 40% granularity is acceptable, K=10 is favored over K=5. The choice is contingent on the acceptable level of data loss. This increased difficulty for attackers stems from the heightened complexity in re-identifying individuals based on sensitive attributes.

However, this approach involves a trade-off, as it results in a loss of granularity in the dataset. The extent of this trade-off depends on the acceptable level of data loss for researchers. L-diversity stipulates that each equivalence class must contain at least l sensitive values, which could potentially increase the size of the classes. The utilization of l-diversity in conjunction with k-anonymity aims to tackle both attribute and identity disclosure, thereby contributing to enhanced privacy measures.

Figure 2: L-Diversity Model Evaluation: Privacy Analysis and Attacker Model Comparison

Experiment 3: In this experiment, the well-known t-closeness privacy model is analyzed. Values from 0.9 to 0.2 for t and k values of 2, 5, 10, and 20 are explored. Addressing attribute disclosure, the t-closeness model is combined with k-anonymity for identity disclosure. The results in Figure 3 show that decreasing the value of t from 0.9 to 0.2 reduces disclosure risk, but it comes at the cost of granularity loss. This reduction in t causes a direct decrease in the disclosure risk against the prosecutor, journalist, and marketer attacker models. Additionally, at some values of K, better granularity is achieved compared to other comparisons. For instance, if 40% granularity is acceptable, K=10 is a better choice than K=5, providing better privacy. Similarly, if 30% granularity is acceptable, K=20 is favored over K=10. The decision hinges on the acceptable level of data loss.

Reducing the t-closeness value indicates a closer resemblance of the distribution of the sensitive attribute in each equivalence class to the overall distribution of the attribute in the original dataset. This feature makes it more challenging for attackers to differentiate individuals based on the sensitive attribute. Nevertheless, decreasing the t-closeness value can also result in a decline in the accuracy of the anonymized dataset. It is because the data may undergo distortion to attain an increased level of privacy protection.

Figure 3: T-Closeness Model Evaluation: Privacy Analysis and Attacker Model Comparison

Experiment 4: In the final experiment, an analysis was conducted on the robust privacy model, differential privacy, known for its strong privacy guarantee. Differential privacy was applied with k-anonymity to enhance privacy. For this model, the analysis included a budget of 10% and delta set to 0.01. Two values of k, namely 2, 5, 10, and 20, were considered. To evaluate the effectiveness, epsilon values ranging from 0.2 to 2 were tested.

A smaller epsilon (ϵ) value signifies a higher level of privacy protection, indicating a strict privacy setting ($\epsilon=0.2$). This setting aims to limit the impact of individual data on the overall dataset privacy. Increasing epsilon relaxes privacy guarantees, allowing for a greater influence of individual records on dataset privacy, with implications for smaller protection, increased data utility, and higher re-identification risk.

Application of this privacy model at different K values did not significantly impact data granularity. However, the risk factor for the attacker model varied at different K values.

Epsilon values ranging from 0.2 to 2 were chosen to evaluate the trade-off between privacy and accuracy. Additionally, the settings of budget and delta were also specified. The budget is the maximum amount of noise that can be added to the data, while delta is the probability that the privacy of a single individual in the dataset could be compromised. The chosen budget and delta settings, 10% and 0.01 respectively, provide a balance between privacy protection and dataset accuracy.

In Figure 4, it is observable that the differential privacy effectively reduces the risk of disclosure of sensitive information, resulting in a higher level of privacy protection for the dataset while maintaining a satisfactory level of utility. Comparing utility with other privacy models, it is relatively low because the primary objective of differential privacy is to ensure enhanced privacy protection. One of the main drawbacks of using differential privacy is that adding noise to the data can potentially reduce the accuracy and utility of the dataset, which can impact the effectiveness of any

downstream analysis or decision-making. Additionally, it can be difficult to determine the optimal level of noise to add to the data to balance privacy and utility, and the process of tuning the privacy parameters can be time-consuming and computationally intensive.

Figure 4: Differential Privacy Model Evaluation: Privacy Analysis and Attacker Model Comparison

Discussion

Each privacy model has its strengths and weaknesses, and the suitability of a particular model depends on the specific scenario and requirements. K-anonymity is suitable when the goal is to protect against re-identification attacks, such as when publishing a dataset. It works well with categorical data and can be applied to both structured and unstructured data. However, it may not be effective against attribute disclosure attacks, and it may result in a loss of data utility. L-diversity is suitable when the goal is to protect against attribute disclosure attacks. It ensures that each equivalence class has a diverse range of values for the sensitive attribute, making it difficult for an attacker to determine the sensitive attribute value of an individual in the class. It works well with categorical and numerical data and can be combined with k-anonymity to provide better privacy protection. T-closeness is suitable when the goal is to protect against attribute disclosure attacks while also preserving data utility. It ensures that the distribution of the sensitive attribute in each equivalence class is close to the overall distribution in the dataset, which makes it difficult for an attacker to distinguish between individuals based on the sensitive attribute. It works well with numerical data but may not be as effective with categorical data. It is especially useful in situations where privacy is a critical concern, and there is a need to balance the utility of the data with the protection of individual privacy. Differential privacy is known for providing a robust framework that quantifies and controls the privacy guarantees, making it suitable for applications where fine-grained control over privacy is essential, such as in healthcare, finance, or any domain dealing with sensitive personal information. It adds random noise to the data to ensure that an attacker cannot determine whether a particular individual is in the dataset, while also preserving the statistical properties of the data. In the realm of differential privacy,

the epsilon parameter serves as a crucial knob, delicately balancing the trade-off between privacy and data utility. A higher epsilon value relaxes privacy constraints, allowing for increased data accuracy and utility but potentially exposing the dataset to a higher risk of re-identification. Conversely, a lower epsilon enhances privacy protection but may result in a more distorted or less informative dataset. The choice of epsilon should be meticulously considered, tailored to the specific privacy requirements and data utility needs of the given application, ensuring a judicious equilibrium between safeguarding individual privacy and preserving the usefulness of the released data.

Differential Privacy is a privacy model that guarantees that the addition or removal of any individual record in the dataset will not significantly affect the privacy of any individual. Differential privacy is very useful when the attacker has auxiliary information that can be used to infer the sensitive attributes of individuals, and is generally considered to be a stronger privacy guarantee than t-closeness. However, differential privacy may also require more noise to be added to the data, which can reduce the utility of the dataset.

So, all privacy models provide some level of privacy protection, but their effectiveness and the level of data utility they provide vary. The k-anonymity model is vulnerable to attacks such as skewness and background knowledge attack, while l-diversity is resistant to these attacks but not to similarity attacks. T-closeness can prevent similarity attacks but is still vulnerable to background knowledge attacks. The ϵ -differential privacy model provides strong privacy guarantees but can significantly reduce the data utility. Based on the results, it is recommended to select a privacy model based on the specific requirements of the dataset and the level of privacy protection needed.

Conclusion

The experiments employed diverse privacy models, each focusing on distinct facets of privacy protection and disclosure risks. The K-anonymity model focused on safeguarding identities, with results indicating a trade-off between increased anonymity (higher k values) and decreased granularity. The l-diversity model, emphasizing attribute disclosure, showcased improved privacy and granularity trade-offs, with the choice of k values influencing the outcome. The t-closeness model, targeting attribute disclosure, demonstrated nuanced results, where decreasing t values enhanced privacy but led to a loss in granularity. The implementation of differential privacy, a robust privacy model, provided strong guarantees, with epsilon values influencing the balance between privacy and utility.

Notably, altering the value of K in the privacy models provided valuable visibility into identifying optimal configurations. Some K values not only yielded improved granularity but also ensured enhanced privacy compared to other K values. This underscores the significance of experimenting with various K values to tailor the privacy model to specific dataset characteristics and privacy requirements.

As the field continues to evolve, future work should focus on further exploring and refining privacy models, considering diverse datasets and application contexts. This will contribute to the ongoing development of effective privacy measures in the rapidly changing landscape of data privacy.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This research received no external funding.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] MURTHY S, BAKAR A A, RAHIM F A, et al. A comparative study of data anonymization techniques; proceedings of the 2019 IEEE 5th Intl Conference on Big Data Security on Cloud (BigDataSecurity), IEEE Intl Conference on High Performance and Smart Computing,(HPSC) and IEEE Intl Conference on Intelligent Data and Security (IDS), F, 2019 [C]. IEEE.
- [2] JOHNY ANTONY P, ANTONY S T. A Review on Privacy Preservation in Big Data [J]. International Journal of Modern Computer Science and Application (IJMCSA) Vol, 4.
- [3] SWEENEY L. k-anonymity: A model for protecting privacy [J]. International journal of uncertainty, fuzziness and knowledge-based systems, 2002, 10(05): 557-570.
- [4] MACHANAVAJJHALA A, KIFER D, GEHRKE J, et al. l-diversity: Privacy beyond k-anonymity [J]. ACM Transactions on Knowledge Discovery from Data (TKDD), 2007, 1(1): 3-es.
- [5] LI N, LI T, VENKATASUBRAMANIAN S. t-closeness: Privacy beyond k-anonymity and l-diversity; proceedings of the 2007 IEEE 23rd international conference on data engineering, F, 2006 [C]. IEEE.
- [6] DWORK C. Differential privacy: A survey of results; proceedings of the Theory and Applications of Models of Computation: 5th International Conference, TAMC 2008, Xi'an, China, April 25-29, 2008 Proceedings 5, F, 2008 [C]. Springer.
- [7] PATIL H K, SESHADRI R. Big data security and privacy issues in healthcare; proceedings of the 2014 IEEE international congress on big data, F, 2014 [C]. IEEE.
- [8] REN X, YANG J. Research on privacy protection based on K-anonymity; proceedings of the 2010 International Conference on Biomedical Engineering and Computer Science, F, 2010 [C]. IEEE.
- [9] OZALP I, GURSOY M E, NERGIZ M E, et al. Privacy-preserving publishing of hierarchical data [J]. ACM Transactions on Privacy and Security (TOPS), 2016, 19(3): 1-29.
- [10] UNITED NATIONS. Universal Declaration of Human Rights [Z]. 1948
- [11] GOLLE P. Revisiting the uniqueness of simple demographics in the US population; proceedings of the Proceedings of the 5th ACM Workshop on Privacy in Electronic Society, F, 2006 [C].
- [12] GOLDBERGER J, TASSA T. Efficient anonymizations with enhanced utility; proceedings of the 2009 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining Workshops, F, 2009 [C]. IEEE.
- [13] DOMINGO-FERRER J, TORRA V. Ordinal, continuous and heterogeneous k-anonymity through microaggregation [J]. Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery, 2005, 11: 195-212.
- [14] WONG R C-W, LI J, FU A W-C, et al. (α , k)-anonymity: an enhanced k-anonymity model for privacy preserving data publishing; proceedings of the Proceedings of the 12th ACM SIGKDD international conference on Knowledge discovery and data mining, F, 2006 [C].
- [15] DOMINGO-FERRER J, TORRA V. A critique of k-anonymity and some of its enhancements; proceedings of the 2008 Third International Conference on Availability, Reliability and Security, F, 2008 [C]. IEEE.
- [16] DOMINGO-FERRER J, SÁNCHEZ D, SORIA-COMAS J. Database anonymization: privacy models, data utility, and microaggregation-based inter-model connections [J]. Synthesis Lectures on Information Security, Privacy, & Trust, 2016, 8(1): 1-136.
- [17] DWORK C. Differential privacy; proceedings of the Automata, Languages and Programming: 33rd International Colloquium, ICALP 2006, Venice, Italy, July 10-14, 2006, Proceedings, Part II 33, F, 2006 [C]. Springer.
- [18] CHEN B-C, KIFER D, LEFEVRE K, et al. Privacy-preserving data publishing [J]. Foundations and Trends® in Databases, 2009, 2(1-2): 1-167.
- [19] JAIN P, GYANCHANDANI M, KHARE N. Big data privacy: a technological perspective and review [J]. Journal of Big Data, 2016, 3: 1-25.

- [20] KUMAR A, GYANCHANDANI M, JAIN P. A comparative review of privacy preservation techniques in data publishing; proceedings of the 2018 2nd International Conference on Inventive Systems and Control (ICISC), F, 2018 [C]. IEEE.
- [21] DOMINGO-FERRER J, SORIA-COMAS J. From t-closeness to differential privacy and vice versa in data anonymization [J]. Knowledge-Based Systems, 2015, 74: 151-158.
- [22] NERGIZ ME, CLIFTON C. Thoughts on k-anonymization [J]. Data & Knowledge Engineering, 2007, 63(3): 622-645.
- [23] BERTINO E, FOVINO I N, PROVENZA L P. A framework for evaluating privacy preserving data mining algorithms [J]. Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery, 2005, 11: 121-154.
- [24] KARR A F, KOHNEN C N, OGANIAN A, et al. A framework for evaluating the utility of data altered to protect confidentiality [J]. The American Statistician, 2006, 60(3): 224-232.
- [25] PRASSER F, KOHLMAYER F. Putting statistical disclosure control into practice: The ARX data anonymization tool [J]. Medical data privacy handbook, 2015: 111-148.